

Recommended citation: Škvor, Z. (2017). Internet Tool Supporting Autonomous Work - 20 Years After . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 820-824). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698271.

Internet tool supporting autonomous work – 20 years after

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ABSTRACT

Assigning each student a proper set of tasks to be solved on his own is an efficient tool in engineering education. Some 20 years ago, AMOS, an automated tool providing for student's autonomous work support has been put into operation at the Faculty of Electrical Eng., CTU Prague. Since then, the system has served to thousands of students. Basic system arrangements as well as some experience gained are shared within the scope of this paper.

Conference Key Areas: Open and Online Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research, Physics and Engineering Education

Keywords: Computer Aided Education

INTRODUCTION

Solving example tasks in a classroom is commonly used in engineering education. Assigning individualized tasks to each student and letting him/her to work on his own is possibly even better. Unfortunately that is also very time consuming. On the other hand, a lot of the work on the teacher side may be automated. Such an automation takes most of the boring tasks off the teacher shoulder, leaving more time for real creative work.

1 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

1.1 Classic approach

Thirty years ago, each individualized task was pre-computed first and then printed on large paper sheets (using mainframe computers or PhD students). Bachelor students have then been assigned tasks with some individual input parameters, mostly read by the teacher. Issuing one task to hundred students took at least one hour. Students visited the poor professor many times to check results against great printed tables, causing numerous interrupts in his work and finally taking several hours of his time before correct solutions were achieved. Sometimes lookup errors in large tables caused incorrect input parameters or even correct replies to be declared incorrect.

1.2 Computerized approach

Each student has a unique identifier. This identifier is used to derive a unique seed number for a pseudo-random number generator. “Random” numbers are then used to create personalized tasks.

First implementation [1] used a list server, tasks were dispatched and results checked using e-mails. Such a solution under Microsoft DOS 3.2 has been in operation between 1997 and 2000. Since then, the system is available through a web page [2]. As operation systems and internet technology evolved, several implementations emerged. Linux Apache server, MySQL and PHP are currently used.

After a student logs in, he can find his tasks and send back his results for automated check any time. At the same time the system records student’s activity so that teachers may learn about their students.

The system keeps all necessary information to support several teachers and students belonging to different study programs, courses and years. Several different scenarios for task composition are in use.

1.3 Simple task example

The simple task scenario consists of a short story – eg. problem description, necessary picture(s) and a fixed set of questions. “Random” input parameters are generated for each student.

To check student answers, closed-form formulas are used to calculate correct replies. Answers are then compared against “exact” values and accepted if they fall within $\pm 2\%$ margins.

Fig. 1. Simple task. Picture used by the system.

An example used in basic electromagnetics course: Two conductive charged balls possessing small diameter a are hanging on two insulated lines of equal length L and negligible weight m , see Fig. 1. Each ball bears a positive charge Q . Coulomb repulsive force keeps the balls apart at mutual distance $2d$. Given a , m , L and d , calculate Q , field strengths E_1 and E_2 , potential ... (abbreviated).

1.4 Complex tasks

While simple tasks are based on closed form formulas, directly coded in PHP language, a number of interesting tasks lack closed form solutions and mostly require more calculation time. Such tasks are solved using in-house solvers and then stored in a database table. To provide for enough versions, 15000 instances are used.

Fig. 2. Complex task example. Picture used by the system.

An example used in electromagnetics course requires numerical solution of a 2-D steady current field. Several electrodes of various cross-section are placed inside a rectangular metallic tube, immersed in conductive media, see Fig. 2. Students are asked to find out currents per unit length, voltages, dissipated power etc., after being taught the basics of numerical solution of static fields using finite-difference method.

1.5 Inverse problems

Inverse problems are quite different from direct ones, the main difference for computer implementation being possibly the existence of a manifold of solutions. While straight problems begin with a set of sources and the unknown results are found as a direct consequence of source presence, inverse problems aim at establishing source(s) that would cause a known field.

As an example, students should provide a set of sources (charged balls, loops, straight wires) along with their position(s) and orientation(s) in order to achieve given electric field strengths at given points of "measurement".

In this case, replies received from students are used to calculate the solution, which is then compared against measurements and the reply is marked as correct if the difference between calculated and “measured” values was small enough. As this calculation must be done within a short time, only problems involving closed form expressions or simple fast iterations are supported.

1.6 Design type problems

Design type problems are important in engineering education. As an example, students should design a matching circuit in order to match a complex load to a 50Ω source at a given frequency or within a given frequency band.

Such problems may involve complex calculations. Quite often, specialized analysis software is available (such as SPICE for electronics) and may be used to handle all the calculation. Student’s design is submitted in a form of a SPICE formatted netlist, parsed and submitted to SPICE for analysis. After obtaining results, AMOS program checks whether the result is compliant with design goals [3].

2 EXPERIENCE GAINED

2.1 AMOS in use

As mentioned above, the system has been in use since 1997. Since then, it runs both in winter and summer terms, where the number of participating teachers/students may be as high as 30/1200 per term. It has been experimentally verified that setting a deadline at the end of a term results in some 95% of students starting with their homework within last two days. Currently we prefer to leave two weeks only for each task, where tasks are evenly distributed over the whole term.

2.2 Time budget

Setting aside initial work, e.g. analysis and programming, time consumption on the side of the professors and his assistants is about five hours per term. Professor introduces the system to students during the first lecture, switches tasks on for a particular subject and time and has to read and reply some e-mails. Assistants log in at the end of term to check student’s results, and may log in regularly to find poorly performing students in order to motivate them. The system provokes some students coming for consultation (not included in the time budget as this is teaching anyway).

Before the system has been introduced, there load on assistants was approximately fifteen minutes per student and task, summing up to some 400 hours in a case of 1200 students and one task only. The worse, this time load was difficult to organize into a continuous time block, resulting on disturbing assistants from other work for several weeks. Some assistants gave up soon and accepted any solution. This used to be a heavy burden limiting any increase in the number of tasks.

2.3 Outcomes

An automated system makes individual student’s work manageable. Proper tasks distributed over the whole term can help students to check their progress and fix problems in time.

The system is used mainly in bachelor level education. AMOS requires numerical replies to be accurate within some limit. This proved to be useful to our bachelor students as they learn that two digit accurate inputs can lead to less accurate results.

2.4 “Universal” online solvers

At a faculty of Electrical engineering with a strong record in informatics, it was a matter of several months only for students to react on the new system. One of the

first tricks used to get around understanding the task(s) itself used a simple algorithm to find a solution for any numerical question in a finite number of simple steps follows:

- 1) Set up a test reply, smaller than any meaningful result (say $1E-22$).
- 2) Send the reply for evaluation; if accepted then done.
- 3) Multiply the current reply by a factor of -1.005 . Proceed with step 2) .

“Solvers” based on similar algorithm increase network traffic a lot, as well as the load on server. Although programming such a solver gives some experience to the student, the original purpose is not met this way. In order to prevent this bypass, a limit on the number of replies one student can send per one task should be set to a proper number (say 25).

2.5 Offline solvers

Soon, some of the students have shared their knowledge (eg. algorithms to solve tasks) in a form of notes, Excel files or even webpages. Although it is still possible to detect students who use “third party” solutions, the author is not in favour of doing so.

Instead of that, some efforts may help to make the case more interesting for students to do it on their own. It is vital to come with “new” tasks, therefore provoking a lot of students crawling for a consultation. It is important to keep the students feeling like a part of an interesting game instead of being simply forced to pass through something. Prizes for students who are the first to solve a new task, as well as prizes for students who find a mistake in the system help to keep the play going on.

3 SUMMARY

Computer programs that provide online support for student’s autonomous work are useful in engineering education - if properly used. Such systems may help students to improve their skills if they wish to do so and help to offload teacher from repeated boring part of the job. Still there is some effort needed from the professor: convincing students to get educated is a job that has no automated solution so far.

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